

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R2.7 Vertical temperature model

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1 INTRODUCTION

The 1D vertical temperature model of the ZA3 borehole was built using PetroMod® together with subsidence and thermal history model of the Zar-3 storage complex. The input data are based on archive data, such as steady state temperature measurements in the wells in a broader neighbourhood of the Zar-3 oil and gas field and thermal conductivity measured on core samples. Lithological properties were adjusted using PetroMod Lithology Editor. The Model was calibrated by the measured data.

2 VERTICAL TEMPERATURE MODEL

2.1 Measured data

Steady state temperature was calculated based on measurements in four wells in the broader area of the Zar-3 oil and gas field: Uhřice UH1, Žarošice ZA1 and ZA2 (Čermák et al, 1992; Myslil et al. 2002). In the ZA3 well temperature was measured using downhole thermometer at depth interval of 1615 – 1800 m in the Vranovice Fm., the rest of the data was calculated (Tab. 2-1 and Fig. 2-1).

Tab. 2-1: Steady state temperature measured and calculated in the wells of the broader Zar-3 oil and gas field.

Depth (m)	Temperature (°C)			
	UH1	ZA1	ZA2	ZA3
0	8	9	8	9
100	11	12	11	12
200	14	15	14	15
300	16	17	16	18
400	18	20	18	21
500	20	23	20	24
600	22	25	22	26
700	24	27	24	29
800	26	29	27	31
900	28	31	30	33
1000	30	33	33	35
1100	32	35	35	38
1200	34	37	37	40
1300	36	39	40	43
1400	38	41	42	45
1500	40	43	45	48
1600	42	46	-	50
1700	-	48	-	52
1800	-	50	-	54
1900	-	53	-	-
2000	-	55	-	-
2100	-	58	-	-
2200	-	61	-	-
2300	-	64	-	-
2400	-	66	-	-
2500	-	69	-	-

Fig. 2-1: Graph of steady state temperatures as a function of depth at wells around the Zar-3 oil and gas field.

Calculated geothermal gradient ranges from 21.25 to 25.0 mK m⁻¹ (i.e. °C km⁻¹). Temperature in the Vranovice Fm. reservoir measured during production range from 50.2 to 54.0 °C at depth of 1615 – 1800 m below the surface. Thermal conductivity and heat capacity of core samples from the wells in the Zar-3 oil & gas field were measured at VŠB Technical University of Ostrava (Tab. 2-2).

Tab. 2-2: Thermal conductivity and heat capacity in the Zar-3 oil and gas field.

Sample name Stratigraphy	TV DSS (m)	Thermal conductivity λ		Heat capacity c_p	
		Average ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) St. dev.		Average ($10^6 \text{ J}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) St. dev.	
UH11_1322 _2_4_20_25 Nesvačilka Fm.	1074.18	2.790	0.000	1.950	0.000
UH-11_1419 _4_3_61_77 Vranovice Fm.	1167.34	2.764	0.035	2.145	0.107
ZA3_1595,5 _3_1_70_90 Vranovice Fm.	1373.09	3.705	0.012	2.211	0.018
ZA3_1595,5 _3_3_70_90 Vranovice Fm.	1375.09	3.623	0.219	2.229	0.062
UH-3_1824 _4_6_70_85 Mikulov Fm.	1538.11	1.922	0.015	1.978	0.032
ZA4A_1759 _1_5_31_46 Vranovice Fm.	1504.93	3.329	0.223	1.868	0.160
ZA4A_1778 _2_5_27_43 Vranovice Fm.	1523.89	2.517	0.028	2.026	0.083
ZA4A_1759 _1_3_44_59 Vranovice Fm.	1503.07	2.255	0.194	1.808	0.143
ZA4A_1759 _1_1_44_59 Vranovice Fm.	1501.07	2.793	0.094	1.941	0.047
ZA4A_1787 _3_3_29_44 Vranovice Fm.	1530.91	2.212	0.106	1.892	0.115
Minimum	1074.18	1.922	0.000	1.808	0.000
Maximum	1538.11	3.705	0.223	2.229	0.160
Average	1409.17	2.791	0.093	2.005	0.077

2.2 1D vertical temperature model including subsidence and thermal history of the ZA3 borehole

Input data for the model

The thermal history model of ZA3 was presented at the PetroMod and Petroleum system Tech Days in Aachen (Francu et al. 2022). The average annual surface temperature ranges from 8 to 9 °C at the thermally neutral zone, where seasonal variations are suppressed. Heat flow density in the area of interest was calculated from the geothermal gradient and thermal conductivity distributions, the values range from 45.2 to 46.1 mW.m⁻² (Čermák et al. 1992; Myslík et al. 2002). This range was used for the model as a starting input parameter.

The main input table for the model is in Tab. 2-3. It defines partial layers of the well profile, respective age of deposition and erosion, thickness of preserved or eroded layers, layer name and lithology. Six key horizons were defined based on lithology and petrophysical properties: three units of the Ždánice nappe (Zdan1, Zdan2, Zdan3), Nesvačilka, Vranovice and Myslejšovice Fms. The additional horizons mentioned in Tab. 2-3 are the eroded units.

Table 2-3: Main input table of the ZA3 temperature and burial history model.

Age	Name	Top	Thickness	Event	Layer	Lithology
Ma	-	(m ssl)	(m)	-	name	-
0.0	Zda_ero	-219	0	Erosion	Zda_ero	-
14.0	Zdan3	-219	484	Deposition	Zdan3	Siltstone (organic lean)
15.0	Zdan2	265	495	Deposition	Zdan2	Sandstone (clay rich)
16.0	Zdan1	760	475	Deposition	Zdan1	Siltstone (organic lean)
17.0	Nes_ero	1235	0	Erosion	Nes_ero	-
30.0	Nesvacilka	1235	111	Deposition	Nesvacilka	Siltstone (organic rich)
47.0	Mikulov_ero	1346	0	Erosion	Mikulov_ero	-
152.0	Mikulov	1346	0	Deposition	Mikulov	Marl
157.0	Vranovice	1346	300	Deposition	Vranovice	Dolomite (organic rich)
163.0	hiatus2	1646	0	Hiatus	-	-
260.0	Mys_ero2	1646	0	Erosion	Mys_ero2	-
300.0	Mys_ero1	1646	0	Erosion	Mys_ero1	-
322.0	hiatus1	1646	0	Hiatus	-	-
324.0	Myslejšovice	1646	202	Deposition	Myslejšovice	Wacke, Sandstone (clay rich), Siltstone
332.0	Cryst	1848	-	-	-	-

The petrophysical properties of the model were optimized using the PetroMod Lithology Editor®. Simulated values of vertical thermal conductivity (W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹) and

heat capacity ($\text{kJ.Kg}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$) of the modelled horizons are in Table 2-4, Figs. 2-2, 2-3 and 2-4.

Table 2-4: Thermal conductivities ($\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$) as a function of temperature and lithology as used in the PetroMod Lithology Editor. For lithology see Tab. 2-3.

Strata	Zdan3	Zdan2	Zdan1	Nesvacilka	Mikulov	Vranovice	Myslejovice
T °C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0	2.07	3.49	2.07	2.03	2.01	2.18	2.24
10	2.06	3.42	2.06	2.02	2.01	2.16	2.22
20	2.05	3.35	2.05	2.01	2.00	2.15	2.21
30	2.04	3.29	2.04	2.00	1.99	2.14	2.19
40	2.03	3.23	2.03	2.00	1.99	2.13	2.18
50	2.03	3.17	2.03	1.99	1.98	2.11	2.17
60	2.02	3.12	2.02	1.98	1.98	2.10	2.15
70	2.01	3.07	2.01	1.98	1.97	2.09	2.14
80	2.01	3.03	2.01	1.97	1.97	2.08	2.13
90	2.00	2.99	2.00	1.97	1.96	2.08	2.12
100	1.99	2.95	1.99	1.96	1.96	2.07	2.11
110	1.99	2.91	1.99	1.96	1.95	2.06	2.10
120	1.98	2.87	1.98	1.96	1.95	2.05	2.09

Fig. 2-2: Thermal conductivity intervals of the reservoir Vranovice Fm. as a function of temperature for parallel and perpendicular direction in respect to stratification. Data trends according to the PetroMod Lithology Editor.

Fig. 2-3: Vertical thermal conductivity ($W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$) of the modelled horizons.

Fig. 2-4: Heat capacity ($kJ.Kg^{-1}.K^{-1}$) of the modelled horizons.

Fig. 2-5: The 1D vertical temperature model in context of subsidence and thermal history of the ZA3 borehole profile built using PetroMod software.

Basal heat flow is the main input parameter together with the thermal conductivity and heat capacity profile (Fig. 2-3 and 2-4). The resulting temperature profile is calibrated by measured data (Fig. 2-6), i.e. the input parameters are modified until an agreement is reached among the modelled and measured data.

Fig. 2-6: The 1D vertical temperature model of the ZA3 borehole profile. Output from the PetroMod 1D with calibration measured temperature points.

Simplified 2D vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 oil and gas field is shown in the W–E geological profile (Figs. 2-7 and 2-8).

Fig. 2-7: W-E profile through the wells ZA1, ZA3 and UH3. Outline of the Zar-3 oil & gas field is shown in purple colour.

Fig. 2-8: Simplified vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 oil and gas field with well trajectories, well logs and geological units building the CO₂-storage complex. Rectangle shows the reservoir temperature and depth interval.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The vertical temperature model was built as a part of the static geometric model and serves as an input for the dynamic model (WP3).

Reservoir temperature in the Vranovice Fm. measured using the downhole thermometer in the ZA3 well ranges from 50.2 to 54.0 °C at depth from 1615 to 1800 m measured from the surface.

Calculated geothermal gradient ranges from 21.25 to 24.7 mK.m⁻¹. The values are notably lower than the average global geothermal gradient 33 mK.m⁻¹.

The average annual surface (neutral zone) temperature ranges from 8 to 9 ° C and represents the starting subsurface value in Tab. 2-1.

In addition to the activities planned in the project, thermal conductivities and heat capacities were measured at the VŠB. Thermal conductivities (λ) of the reservoir rocks range from 2.72 to 3.94 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ with average of 3.37 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹. Heat capacities (c_p) range from 1.95 to 2.30 10⁶ J.m⁻³.K⁻¹ with average of 2.17 10⁶ J.m⁻³.K⁻¹.

Heat flow density in the area of interest calculated from the geothermal gradient and thermal conductivity distributions ranges from 45.2 to 46.1 mW.m⁻² (Čermák et al. 1992; Myslík et al. 2002).

The PetroMod thermal model provides not only isolated datapoints but a complete depth profile of thermal conductivity and heat capacity. This may be used for further dynamic modeling of the CO₂ injection associated with cooling of the rocks.

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